

GSERB: A Novel Attention-Integrated Ghost Residual Block for Enhanced DoA Estimation

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Abstract—This paper presents a lightweight neural architecture for efficient direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation, built upon a novel Ghost Squeeze-and-Excitation Residual Block (GSERB). The proposed block integrates Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention directly into the Ghost feature generation process, enabling selective channel enhancement while minimizing redundant feature computation. Unlike conventional attention-augmented convolutional networks, the GSERB amplifies informative ghost feature channels prior to fusion with intrinsic representations, thereby improving feature discrimination and representational efficiency. Experimental results showcase that this integration enhances the model’s ability to capture spatial-spectral dependencies while maintaining a compact design. The resulting network, named GSERB-DoANet, achieves an effective balance between accuracy, scalability, and computational efficiency for real-time multi-source DoA estimation in wireless sensing applications.

Index Terms—Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation, Attention Mechanisms, Deep Learning, Lightweight Networks, Wireless Communications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation plays a fundamental role in modern wireless communication and sensing systems, underpinning key functionalities, including adaptive beamforming, source localization, interference suppression, and spatial multiplexing in massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) and beyond-5G (B5G) networks. Traditional subspace-based algorithms, e.g., multiple signal classification (MUSIC) [1] and estimation of signal parameters via rotational invariance techniques (ESPRIT) [2], provide high angular resolution and asymptotically accurate estimates under idealized conditions. However, their performance deteriorates significantly in practical scenarios characterized by low signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs), correlated multipath components, or a limited number of temporal snapshots.

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In contrast, data-driven approaches using deep neural networks have recently shown great potential in providing robust and efficient DoA estimation without relying on strict assumptions. The deployment of deep networks in real-time and edge-oriented applications remains challenging due to their computational complexity and large memory footprint. Lightweight convolutional architectures, e.g., MobileNet [6] and ShuffleNet [7], have been introduced to reduce redundancy in feature maps through cheap transformations. These methods achieve efficiency gains, although they often compromise discriminative power, as redundant or weak feature representations may still propagate through the network.

In conventional convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a significant proportion of feature maps are highly redundant, leading to unnecessary computation and parameter overhead. CNNs have been applied to spatial spectrum learning [3], covariance-based DoA estimation [4], and multi-source localization [5]. GhostNet [8] addresses this inefficiency by generating intrinsic feature maps through standard convolutions and then deriving additional “ghost” feature maps using inexpensive linear transformations, such as depthwise convolutions. These ghost features effectively mimic the information content of conventional convolutional outputs while requiring substantially fewer operations. These cheaply generated ghost maps are obtained through simple transformations, thus they may contain redundant or low-salience information, which can degrade feature discriminability—particularly in fine-grained spatial estimation tasks such as DoA prediction.

Attention mechanisms have proven highly effective in improving feature selectivity in computer vision and signal processing tasks. The squeeze-and-excitation (SE) block [9] adaptively reweights channel responses based on global context, while the convolutional block attention module [10] extends this concept to spatial attention. These methods, however, are applied after full convolutional operations, adding overhead and reducing suitability for lightweight designs. Recent efforts to integrate attention into compact CNNs [11], [12] have

shown promise but lack specialized adaptation for array signal processing tasks.

To the authors' best knowledge, no existing work has explored the integration of channel attention mechanisms directly within the Ghost feature generation process for array signal processing and DoA estimation. This paper addresses this gap by introducing a novel Ghost-SE residual block (GSERB), a hybrid neural building block that integrates channel attention directly into the ghost feature generation process. Unlike conventional attention-augmented CNNs, which apply SE after convolutions, GSERB applies selective weighting to ghost feature channels before their concatenation with intrinsic features. This design enables the network to suppress redundant information and enhance the contribution of informative feature maps with minimal additional cost. Embedding GSERB within a residual framework further stabilizes training and promotes feature reuse, achieving a strong balance between accuracy, efficiency, and scalability. Building on this foundation, we design a lightweight neural architecture tailored for real-time DoA estimation in edge and embedded devices. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II outlines the system model and problem formulation, Section III details the proposed GSERB module and network architecture, Section IV presents and discusses the results. Finally Section V concludes the paper and highlights future research directions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND DATASET ANALYSIS

We consider a uniform linear array (ULA) consisting of M omnidirectional antenna elements, equally spaced by distance d . The array receives K narrowband far-field plane waves impinging from distinct azimuth directions $\{\theta_k\}_{k=1}^K$. The received complex baseband snapshot at time index t is modeled as

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{a}(\theta_k) s_k(t) + \mathbf{n}(t), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{a}(\theta_k) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the steering vector for direction θ_k , $s_k(t)$ denotes the source signal, and $\mathbf{n}(t)$ represents additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with variance σ^2 . For a ULA aligned along the x -axis, the steering vector is defined as

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta_k) = \left[1, e^{-j \frac{2\pi d}{\lambda} \sin \theta_k}, \dots, e^{-j \frac{2\pi d}{\lambda} (M-1) \sin \theta_k} \right]^T, \quad (2)$$

where λ is the carrier wavelength. Under this model, the array output can be compactly written as

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{s}(t) + \mathbf{n}(t), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_K)]$ and $\mathbf{s}(t) = [s_1(t), \dots, s_K(t)]^T$. The spatial covariance matrix, that will be used as the learning input in our model, is obtained as

$$\mathbf{R}_x = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{x}(t)\mathbf{x}^H(t)\} = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{R}_s\mathbf{A}^H(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + \sigma^2\mathbf{I}_M, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_s = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{s}(t)\mathbf{s}^H(t)\}$ is the source covariance matrix.

To train and validate the proposed model, a synthetic dataset was generated using a simulation framework that emulates realistic array signal conditions. For each data sample, K

sources were randomly placed at distinct azimuth angles $\theta_k \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$, with random complex amplitudes and temporal phases. The number of impinging signals K varies across experiments, ranging from one to five, to evaluate the model's ability to generalize under different source configurations.

Snapshots $\mathbf{x}(t)$ were synthesized according to (1) with varying signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) levels ranging from -10 to 20 dB. Each covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_x was estimated from T snapshots using

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbf{x}(t)\mathbf{x}^H(t), \quad (5)$$

and subsequently normalized by its trace to improve numerical stability during network training.

The real and imaginary parts of $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x$ are concatenated as two separate input channels:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}} = [\Re(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x), \Im(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x)], \quad (6)$$

producing a compact $2 \times M \times M$ tensor representation. This format is compatible with convolutional architectures while preserving full spatial correlation information. During experimentation, we observed that the phase component of the complex covariance matrix carries additional discriminative information related to the relative propagation delays between array elements. Therefore, an additional channel representing the element-wise phase $\angle(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x)$ is included, defined as

$$\angle(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x) = \arctan \left(\frac{\Im(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x)}{\Re(\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x)} \right), \quad (7)$$

resulting in a $3 \times M \times M$ input tensor. 80% of the samples were used for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing.

III. MODEL ARCHITECTURE AND PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Analysis of Ghost Feature Generation

GhostNet introduces a decomposition of feature generation into intrinsic and ghost feature maps to reduce convolutional redundancy. For a standard convolutional layer that produces n output feature maps from m input channels, the computational cost is proportional to $O(mnk^2)$, where k is the kernel size. Ghost convolution decomposes this process as

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}} = \text{Conv}(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{W}_1), \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{ghost}} = \text{CheapOps}(\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}; \mathbf{W}_2), \quad (9)$$

where CheapOps(\cdot) are inexpensive depthwise or linear transformations that expand intrinsic features \mathbf{F}_{int} into additional ghost maps $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ghost}}$. The concatenated feature set is

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{out}} = [\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}, \mathbf{F}_{\text{ghost}}]. \quad (10)$$

Although efficient, this process could potentially propagate redundant or noisy ghost features with equal importance, reducing discriminative power.

B. Channel Attention and SE Blocks

SE blocks address channel redundancy by adaptively recalibrating feature responses. Given a feature tensor $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$, the SE operation consists of three stages:

- 1) Squeeze: Global average pooling aggregates spatial information into channel descriptors:

$$z_c = \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W F_c(i, j). \quad (11)$$

- 2) Excitation: A two-layer fully connected bottleneck learns channel dependencies:

$$\mathbf{w} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_2 \delta(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{z})), \quad (12)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is ReLU and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is Sigmoid activation.

- 3) Recalibration: Channel-wise rescaling enhances informative features:

$$\mathbf{F}'_c = w_c \cdot \mathbf{F}_c. \quad (13)$$

While SE improves feature selectivity, it incurs additional parameter and computation overhead when applied across all channels and layers.

C. Proposed GSERB Architecture

Unlike prior hybrid models that simply stack SE after Ghost modules, GSERB integrates channel attention within the ghost feature generation process to enable early selective enhancement of useful ghost features before concatenation. Given an input feature map $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$, the GSERB module first extracts the intrinsic feature representation through a standard convolutional transformation:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}} = \text{Conv}(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{W}_1), \quad (14)$$

followed by

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{ghost}} = \text{CheapOps}(\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}; \mathbf{W}_2), \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{W}_1 represents the convolutional kernel weights responsible for extracting the intrinsic feature maps that encode the essential spatial and spectral correlations in the input \mathbf{X} . The subsequent operation uses \mathbf{W}_2 , which corresponds to the lightweight transformation kernels applied in the cheap feature generation stage. These kernels are typically implemented as depthwise or grouped convolutions to synthesize additional “ghost” feature maps at minimal computational cost, leveraging the redundancy present in \mathbf{F}_{int} .

To enhance the discriminative capability of these ghost features, a channel-wise attention mechanism is applied directly to $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ghost}}$. This mechanism utilizes global average pooling (GAP) followed by two fully connected layers with a bottleneck structure and nonlinear activations:

$$\mathbf{w} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_4 \delta(\mathbf{W}_3 \text{GAP}(\mathbf{F}_{\text{ghost}}))), \quad (16)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ and $\sigma(\cdot)$ denote the ReLU and sigmoid activations, respectively. The resulting weight vector \mathbf{w} encodes channel-wise importance information, allowing the model to selectively

emphasize informative ghost channels while suppressing redundant or noisy ones.

The recalibrated ghost features are then obtained through element-wise modulation:

$$\mathbf{F}'_{\text{ghost}} = \mathbf{w} \odot \mathbf{F}_{\text{ghost}}, \quad (17)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication between the attention weights and the corresponding ghost feature maps. This selective enhancement ensures that only the most relevant ghost responses contribute to the final feature representation. Finally, the intrinsic and attention-weighted ghost features are concatenated, batch-normalized, and fused with the input through a residual connection to stabilize training and facilitate gradient flow:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \text{BN}([\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}, \mathbf{F}'_{\text{ghost}}]) + \mathbf{X}, \quad (18)$$

where \odot denotes channel-wise multiplication, GAP is global average pooling, and BN represents batch normalization. The residual shortcut ensures stable gradient propagation and prevents vanishing during deep-layer training.

The complete DoA estimation model, termed as GSERBNet, stacks multiple GSERB layers with increasing channel depth followed by global average pooling and a dense classification head:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = f_{\Theta}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}}) = \text{Softmax}(\text{FC}(\text{GAP}(\mathcal{G}_L(\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}})))), \quad (19)$$

where $\mathcal{G}_L(\cdot)$ denotes the sequential application of L GSERB blocks.

D. Output Representation and Decoding

The proposed network formulates DoA estimation as a discrete regression problem over a fixed angular grid

$$\mathcal{G} = \{\theta_g \mid \theta_g = -60^\circ, -59^\circ, \dots, 60^\circ\},$$

with $G = 121$ bins and resolution $\Delta\theta = 1^\circ$. The network outputs a vector $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \in \mathbb{R}^G$, transformed via softmax to a probability distribution

$$\mathbf{p} = \text{softmax}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}), \quad p_g = \frac{e^{\hat{y}_g}}{\sum_{h=1}^G e^{\hat{y}_h}}. \quad (20)$$

Ground-truth directions $\Theta = \{\theta^{(1)}, \dots, \theta^{(K)}\}$ are encoded as a multi-hot vector $\mathbf{y} \in \{0, 1\}^G$, where $y_g = 1$ if $|\theta^{(k)} - \theta_g| \leq \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}$ for any k .

Instead of explicitly decomposing \mathbf{R}_x as in classical subspace approaches, we employ a data-driven neural mapping

$$f_{\Theta} : \mathbf{R}_x \mapsto \hat{\mathbf{y}}, \quad (21)$$

parameterized by Θ , where $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \in \mathbb{R}^G$ represents the estimated spatial energy distribution across an angular grid $\{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_G\}$. The network learns to approximate

$$\hat{y}_i \approx \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \delta(\theta_i - \theta_k), \quad (22)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ denotes the Dirac delta and α_k is a power weighting term. The final estimated DoAs correspond to the peaks in $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, i.e.,

$$\hat{\Theta} = \{\theta_i \mid \hat{y}_i \in \text{Top-}K(\hat{\mathbf{y}})\}. \quad (23)$$

E. Bayesian Hyperparameter Optimization

The selection of optimal hyperparameters for the proposed GSERB-based DoA estimation network was performed using Bayesian optimization, which efficiently balances exploration and exploitation when evaluating computationally expensive models. Let $\lambda \in \Lambda$ denote a candidate hyperparameter configuration from the search space Λ , and let $f(\lambda)$ represent the validation F1-score obtained by training the model with configuration λ . The goal is to determine

$$\lambda^* = \arg \max_{\lambda \in \Lambda} f(\lambda), \quad (24)$$

where f lacks a closed-form expression and each evaluation requires a full training cycle.

To address this, Bayesian optimization constructs a probabilistic surrogate model of f , typically a Gaussian Process (GP), which estimates the posterior distribution based on previously observed trials $\mathcal{D}_n = \{(\lambda_i, f(\lambda_i))\}_{i=1}^n$. The GP is defined as

$$f(\lambda) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\lambda), k(\lambda, \lambda')), \quad (25)$$

where $m(\lambda)$ is the mean function and $k(\lambda, \lambda')$ is the kernel function. The posterior mean and variance for a candidate λ are obtained as:

$$\mu_n(\lambda) = m(\lambda) + \mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{K}^{-1}(\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{m}), \quad (26)$$

$$\sigma_n^2(\lambda) = k(\lambda, \lambda) - \mathbf{k}^\top \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{k}, \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the kernel matrix over the observed samples, \mathbf{k} the covariance vector between λ and the sampled points, and \mathbf{f} the corresponding observed function values.

In practice, the tree-structured parzen (TPE) estimator implementation of Optuna [13] is adopted. Instead of modeling f directly, TPE models the conditional density $p(\lambda \mid f(\lambda))$ by splitting observations into two groups: configurations yielding good performance $f(\lambda) < f^*$, and others. These are described by probability densities $\ell(\lambda)$ and $g(\lambda)$ respectively:

$$p(\lambda \mid f(\lambda) < f^*) = \ell(\lambda), \quad p(\lambda \mid f(\lambda) \geq f^*) = g(\lambda). \quad (28)$$

The acquisition function guiding the search is then defined as

$$\alpha(\lambda) = \frac{\ell(\lambda)}{g(\lambda)}, \quad (29)$$

and the next configuration is chosen by maximizing this ratio:

$$\lambda_{n+1} = \arg \max_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \alpha(\lambda \mid \mathcal{D}_n). \quad (30)$$

The hyperparameter search space encompassed both architectural and training parameters. Architectural parameters included the number of GSERB blocks $n_{\text{blocks}} \in \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$, per-block channel dimensions $c_i \in \{256, 512, 768, 1024, 1280\}$, SE reduction ratio $r_{se} \in \{2, 4, 8\}$, ghost ratio $\rho \in \{2, 3, 4\}$, and dropout rate $p_{\text{drop}} \in [0.0, 0.5]$ with step 0.1. Training parameters included batch size $B \in \{16, 32, 64\}$. The resulting configuration space $|\Lambda|$ is on the order of 10^6 , rendering exhaustive search impractical. The Bayesian optimization process was initialized with 10 random evaluations to bootstrap the surrogate model, followed by 30 TPE-guided trials. Each trial involved training for 50 epochs with early stopping, using the Adam optimizer ($\eta_0 = 10^{-3}$), gradient clipping ($\|\nabla \theta\|_2 \leq 1$), and a ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler (patience = 2, factor = 0.5). The dataset corresponded to SNR = 10 dB and 200 temporal snapshots, serving as a representative environment for optimization. The optimal configuration consisted of four GSERB blocks with progressively increasing channel widths 256, 512, 768, 1024, a ghost ratio of 2, SE reduction ratio of 4, and dropout rate of 0.2.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

To assess the performance of the proposed GSERB-DoANet, we evaluate the angular prediction accuracy using two complementary metrics: mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE). Mean absolute error (MAE) quantifies the average deviation between the estimated and true source angles:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K |\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i|. \quad (31)$$

Root mean square error (RMSE) emphasizes larger deviations by penalizing higher errors quadratically:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K (\hat{\theta}_i - \theta_i)^2}. \quad (32)$$

The evaluation is conducted using a synthetic dataset of narrowband far-field signals, the ULA consists of $M = 8$ omnidirectional sensors spaced at half-wavelength distance ($d = 0.5\lambda$). Each snapshot is corrupted by additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN), and signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) are varied from -10 dB to 20 dB. For each SNR level, 100,000 test samples are generated. For comparative evaluation, we select three widely used lightweight convolutional neural network architectures: MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and Ghost-ResNet. MobileNetV2 is a depthwise-separable CNN optimized for mobile and embedded applications, providing a strong baseline for efficient feature extraction. ShuffleNetV2 is designed for low-latency inference with channel shuffling and pointwise group convolutions, making it suitable for real-time scenarios. Ghost-ResNet incorporates Ghost modules within a residual network, emphasizing parameter efficiency and reduced computational cost while retaining representational

capacity. These models represent the current state-of-the-art in lightweight, high-efficiency CNN design and offer relevant performance benchmarks for evaluating the accuracy, inference time, and parameter efficiency of the proposed GSERB-DoANet.

A. Accuracy Comparison vs SNR

Table I presents the angular estimation performance of GSERB-DoANet in comparison with MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and Ghost-ResNet under varying SNR conditions for $K = 2$ sources and $L = 200$ snapshots. At low SNR (-10 dB), GSERB-DoANet achieves an MAE of 4.97° and an RMSE of 15.42° , significantly outperforming MobileNetV2 and ShuffleNetV2, which report MAEs of 11.77° and 6.94° , respectively. These results indicate that the integrated Ghost-SE residual blocks effectively suppress noise and extract salient spatial features even in challenging low-SNR scenarios. As the SNR increases, all models show a decrease in estimation errors; however, GSERB-DoANet consistently outperforms the baselines. At 0 dB, it achieves an MAE of 0.59° and an RMSE of 2.47° , representing relative improvements of 94.0% , 51.1% , and 45.1% over MobileNetV2, ShuffleNetV2, and Ghost-ResNet, respectively.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF GSERB-DOANET AND LIGHTWEIGHT CNN BASELINES ($K = 2$ SOURCES, $L = 200$ SNAPSHOTS).

Model	SNR (dB)	MAE ($^\circ$)	RMSE ($^\circ$)
GSERB-DoANet	-10	4.97	15.42
	-5	1.62	7.41
	0	0.59	2.47
	5	0.41	1.33
	10	0.34	0.88
	15	0.32	0.80
	20	0.31	0.71
MobileNetV2	-10	11.77	24.92
	-5	10.98	24.21
	0	9.83	21.48
	5	5.07	16.52
	10	2.03	9.46
	15	1.81	9.33
	20	1.05	8.62
ShuffleNetV2	-10	6.94	17.43
	-5	2.35	10.53
	0	1.21	8.83
	5	0.91	8.46
	10	0.86	8.32
	15	0.75	8.13
	20	0.68	8.01
Ghost-ResNet	-10	6.69	16.62
	-5	2.82	11.62
	0	1.08	5.63
	5	0.78	3.69
	10	0.64	3.02
	15	0.62	3.00
	20	0.62	2.86

In the high-SNR regime (≥ 10 dB), the proposed model approaches near-ideal angular resolution, with MAE below 0.35° and RMSE under 1.0° . Beyond absolute accuracy,

GSERB-DoANet exhibits lower error variance and a smoother performance trend across SNR levels, reflecting strong robustness and generalization capability. These results highlight the effectiveness of combining Ghost feature generation with SE attention in achieving precise, reliable, and noise-resilient DoA estimation.

B. Computational Efficiency

Table II reports the inference latency for all models under identical testing conditions. GSERB-DoANet achieves the fastest inference with an average runtime of 3.0 ms per covariance sample, over $2.2\times$ faster than MobileNetV2 and $2.7\times$ faster than ShuffleNetV2. The near-constant inference time across all SNRs indicates stable forward propagation complexity, further supporting its suitability for real-time or embedded applications.

TABLE II
AVERAGE INFERENCE TIME COMPARISON OF GSERB-DOANET AND BASELINE MODELS ($K = 2$ SOURCES, $L = 200$ SNAPSHOTS).

Model	Inference Time (ms)
GSERB-DoANet	3.00
MobileNetV2	6.73
ShuffleNetV2	8.08
Ghost-ResNet	5.35

C. Multi-Source Scalability

Table III summarizes GSERB-DoANet's performance for varying numbers of sources ($K = 1$ to 5) at 0 dB SNR. The model maintains excellent scalability, with only gradual performance degradation as the number of simultaneous emitters increases. The MAE remains below 1° for up to three sources and rises gracefully thereafter, confirming the network's generalization capability in multi-source environments.

TABLE III
GSERB-DOANET SCALABILITY PERFORMANCE WITH VARYING NUMBER OF SOURCES ($L = 200$, SNR = 0 DB).

Sources	MAE ($^\circ$)	RMSE ($^\circ$)	F1-score	Time (ms)
1	0.53	0.64	0.35	3.01
2	0.59	2.47	0.47	3.05
3	1.84	7.85	0.50	3.89
4	4.37	12.44	0.45	3.72
5	5.62	13.40	0.44	3.00

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented GSERB and integrated it into GSERB-DoANet, a lightweight deep learning framework for multi-source DoA estimation that integrates Ghost convolutional bottlenecks, SE recalibration, and residual connections within a unified block design. The architecture was systematically optimized to balance representational capacity and computational efficiency, resulting in a compact model with low inference

latency. Experimental evaluation demonstrates that GSERB-DoANet consistently outperforms existing lightweight CNN baselines across a range of SNR conditions, maintaining robust performance even under challenging noise scenarios. Its efficient processing of spatial covariance matrices and fine-grained angular resolution, combined with scalability to multiple sources, make it highly suitable for real-time deployment in edge and embedded array processing systems. Future research should focus on extending GSERB-DoANet to three-dimensional DoA estimation and broadband signal scenarios, incorporating temporal modeling for dynamic source tracking, and exploring neural architecture search to further automate the design of efficient beamforming-aware feature extractors.

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